

ON THE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE PIEZORESISTIVITY OF EMBEDDED CARBON FIBRES

Alexander Horoschenkoff, Tobias Mueller, Andreas Kroell
Munich University of Applied Sciences
Department of Mechanical, Automotive and Aeronautical Engineering
Dachauer Str. 98b
80335 Munich
Germany
alexander.horoschenkoff@hm.edu

SUMMARY

The piezoresistivity of carbon fibres has become a key property for exploiting the electrical conductivity of carbon fibres in the development of smart composite structures. Commercially available carbon fibres (ex-PAN and ex-pitch) were electrically connected at the fibres' ends by means of a galvanic process. In order to characterize the piezoresistivity of the embedded carbon fibres, specific specimens were employed. To avoid a short circuit between the carbon-fibre sensor and the laminate, glass-fibre-reinforced plastics were used for all specimens. Different lay-ups were used to determine the strain sensitivity k , the influence of high strain levels, and the influence of laminate micro-cracks. Strain levels from 1,000 to 6,000 $\mu\text{m/m}$ were applied; at each strain level 10 tensile load cycles were investigated. The investigation showed that commercially available ex-PAN fibres (Toray T300B) exhibit excellent linear behaviour for strain levels up to 6,000 $\mu\text{m/m}$. A strain sensitivity k of 1.71 was determined. The ex-pitch fibre investigated (Nippon Graphite Fibre CN 90) exhibits nonlinear behaviour. Micro-cracks in a laminate having a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ lay-up could be detected by means of ex-PAN as well as ex-pitch fibres. The investigation showed that the specific specimens developed can be applied to characterize the piezoresistivity of embedded carbon fibres. Carbon-fibre sensors offer a high potential for use as a sensor element for composite materials for a variety of applications, such as stress analysis, damage detection, and the monitoring of manufacturing processes and quality. Several carbon-fibres can be arranged to get a smart sensor mesh.

Keywords: Smart materials, carbon fibre, piezoresistivity, electrical properties, sensor

INTRODUCTION

In view of exhaustible raw materials and the need to save energy, light-weight engineering and design have become key technologies for many types of construction. Compared to metals, carbon-fibre-reinforced plastics feature excellent specific mechanical properties, which will lead to a new focus on this material. In addition to their excellent mechanical properties, carbon fibres also exhibit electrical conductivity. Depending on the fibre type, the specific resistivity varies from 3 $\mu\Omega\text{m}$ for ex-pitch to 18 $\mu\Omega\text{m}$ for ex-PAN fibres. The electrical behaviour also permits using the carbon fibre

as the sensor element. Embedded in the composite materials, this carbon-fibre sensor could be used to improve the performance of many applications, such as rotor blades for windmills, drive shafts or spring elements. Within this context, the piezoresistivity of carbon fibres has become a key property and was evaluated for commercially available carbon fibres (ex-PAN and ex-pitch). Furthermore a smart sensor mesh can be designed by the arrangement of several carbon-fibre sensors.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The resistance R of a fibre is yielded by:

$$R = \rho \frac{l}{r^2 \pi}$$

where ρ is the specific resistivity, l is the length and r the radius of the fibre. The piezoresistivity of the fibre is then yielded by the following definition:

$$\frac{dR}{R} = k \varepsilon = \varepsilon(1 + 2\nu) + \frac{d\rho}{\rho}; \quad \varepsilon = \frac{dl}{l}; \quad \nu = \frac{-dr/r}{dl/l}$$

where k is the strain sensitivity, ε is the applied strain and ν is the Poisson ratio. While the term $\varepsilon(1 + 2\nu)$ represents the geometric effects, the term $d\rho/\rho$ describes the piezoresistivity.

It should be taken into consideration that the strain sensitivity k is influenced by the longitudinal deformation of the laminate ε_l and the transverse deformation ε_q . This results in the following equation, where k_l is the sensitivity in fibre direction and k_q is the sensitivity transverse to the fibre direction.

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R} = k_l \varepsilon_l + k_q \varepsilon_q$$

Therefore the strain sensitivity is defined for a specific Poisson's ratio, which is 0.285 for conventional strain gauges.

EXPERIMENTAL

The investigation was performed for one ex-PAN fibre (Toray T300B) and one ex-pitch fibre (Nippon Graphite Fibre CN 90). Each roving was prepared to consist of about 1,000 filaments, and was 160 mm long. For fibre preparation, a galvanic process was applied based on a nickel electrolyte. A current of 40 and 170 mA was applied for 30 seconds in order to intercept a coating at the end of the fibre only. The electrical connection was finalized by soldering pins. The electrical connection is only 5 mm long (see Figures 1 and 2). Therefore, the gauge length of the pure carbon fibre is 150 mm.

The fibres were embedded using three different types of specimens in order to evaluate the piezoresistivity, the influence of the electrical connection, and the influence of damage to the laminate on the sensor signal. An overview of the design of the different

specimens used is given in Table 1. The carbon-fibre sensor is embedded in the symmetry plane of the specimen.

Figures 1 and 2: Electrical connection at the end of the carbon-fibre sensor

A homogeneous strain level along the carbon fibre is necessary to determine the strain sensitivity factor k , which is the case if a tensile load is applied. The stacking sequence of this specimen is $[0, 0, 0, 0]_{\text{sym}}$. Therefore no damage to the laminate, which would influence the sensor signal, is expected.

Different problems may occur at the end of the fibre, where the electrical connection of the fibre is located at higher strain levels. At this area inhomogeneous stress levels and damage to the fibres due to the galvanic process may occur. In order to avoid any influence of the electrical connection, tabs were applied for a second type of specimen (see Figure 3). These tabs have the stacking sequence $[-45, +45, 0, 0, 0]_{\text{sym}}$, which ensure that the strain level in the area of the electrical connection is four times smaller compared to the gauge length. Consequently, the influence of the electrical connection is rather small. Damage to the carbon-fibre sensor will determine the detected signal, if the stacking sequence of the gauge length is $[0, 0, 0, 0]_{\text{sym}}$.

Finally, specimen having the stacking sequence $[0, 90, 90, 90, 90, 90, 0]_{\text{sym}}$ were investigated, too. Since micro-cracks will appear in the 90° layers at strain levels higher than $4,000 \mu\text{m}/\text{m}$, the influence of damage to the laminate on the sensor signal can be analyzed using the third type of specimen.

Figure 3: Technical description of the specimen having tabs

Table 1: Overview of the different specimens

	Stacking sequence of the gauge length	Stacking sequence of the tabs	Objective
0° laminate without tabs	$[0,0,0,0]_{\text{sym}}$	No tabs	Determination of strain sensitivity k
0° laminate with tabs	$[0,0,0,0]_{\text{sym}}$	$[-45, +45, 0, 0, 0]_{\text{sym}}$	Fibre characterization at high strain levels
0°/90° laminate with tabs	$[0,90,90,90,90, 90, 0]_{\text{sym}}$	$[-45, +45, 0, 0, 0]_{\text{sym}}$	Influence of laminate damage on the signal

Three carbon-fibre sensors were embedded in one specimen. To avoid a short circuit between the carbon-fibre sensor and the laminate, glass-fibre-reinforced plastics (Hexcel 914) were used for all specimens. The laminates were cured by means of a vacuum bag in an oven for 1 hour at 180° C. The tabs are manufactured separately and bonded to the specimen. To compensate for temperature, a half-bridge was used by means of a second, unstressed specimen (Figure 4). The feeding voltage of the amplifier (HBM Spider 8) was 2.5 V. A strain gauge (HBM: RY 11-10-120) was used to determine the strain level and the strain sensitivity k of the carbon-fibre sensor. The cyclic tensile load was applied by a universal testing machine (Zwick 1465) having a hydraulic clamping device.

Figure 4: Experimental set-up

RESULTS

Figure 5 shows the behaviour of fibre T300 embedded in the 0° laminate having tabs to lower the stress level at the electric connections. As can be seen, the fibre features excellent linear behaviour up to strain levels of 6,000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$. The scattering is less than 2%, considering the 10 load cycles applied. The strain gauge and the carbon-fibre sensor exhibit the same basic behaviour. Neither damage to the laminate nor the fibre can be observed.

Figure 5: Ex-PAN fibre: 10 load cycles at a strain level of 6,000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ for the 0° laminate with tabs

Figure 6: Ex-PAN fibre: 10 load cycles at a strain level of 2,000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ for 0° laminate without tabs

Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the behaviour of the specimen having the same carbon fibre and the same stacking sequence, but no tabs. Since a homogeneous strain level is present, the strain sensitivity k can be determined. Figure 6 shows the behaviour for a strain level of $2,000 \mu\text{m/m}$. The strain sensitivity k of 1.71 can be evaluated. The Poisson's ratio of the specimen was 0.28. At higher strain levels, the carbon sensor fibre exhibits nonlinear behaviour (Figure 7). Furthermore, the resistivity is seen to decrease more and more for each load cycle. This can be attributed to damage at the electrical connection points, showing poor loading capacity.

Figure 8 shows the influence of laminate damage on the sensor signal. The laminate has a stacking sequence of $0^\circ/90^\circ$. A strain level of more than $3,000 \mu\text{m/m}$ will generate micro-cracks in the 90° layers, which can be detected by means of the fibres. In order to avoid any influence of the electrical connection, tabs are used for this specimen. Due to the damage to the laminate, an increase in the resistivity of about 1 - 2% can be detected if the specimen is stressed. Due to the results of the 0° specimen, it can be assumed that there is no damage to the ex-PAN fibre itself or the electrical connection. Micro-cracks in the 90° layers could be verified by means of microscopic inspection (Figure 9). A good correlation between the sensor signal $\Delta R/R_0$ and the crack density could be observed.

Figure 7: Ex-PAN fibre: 10 load cycles at a strain level of $6,000 \mu\text{m/m}$ for 0° laminate without tabs

Figure 8: Ex-PAN fibre: 10 load cycles at a strain level of 6,000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ for the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate with tabs

Figure 9: Micrograph for the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ specimen with tabs and ex-PAN fibre

Figures 10 and 11 show the results for the ex-pitch fibres. Figure 10 shows the results of the ex-pitch fibre for the 0° specimen with tabs to investigate the overall behaviour of the fibre. As can be seen, the fibre behaviour is nonlinear. Furthermore, damage to the fibres can be detected, since an increase in the resistivity can be detected for each load cycle. The behaviour corresponds to the maximum elongation of ex-pitch fibres. At higher strain levels the increase in resistivity is remarkably high ($>60\%$), due to damage to the fibre. Only small changes in the resistivity ($<3\%$) could be measured for the unstressed damaged fibres.

Figure 10: Ex-pitch fibre: 10 load cycles at a strain level of 2,500 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ for the 0° laminate with tabs

OUTLOOK

Carbon-fibre sensors offer a high potential for use as a sensor element for composite materials for a variety of applications, such as stress analysis, damage detection, and the monitoring of manufacturing processes and quality. Several carbon-fibres can be arranged to get a smart sensor mesh. Figure 11 shows the thermal image of a specimen with an integrated carbon-fibre sensor mesh. The carbon-fibre sensor mesh was used for heating and damage detection in the centre of the specimen. The investigation showed that carbon-fibre sensors can sustain high strain levels occurring in composite structures. In comparison with strain gauges measuring punctiform, carbon-fibre sensors deliver an integral strain level. Therefore new tools based on approaches from finite element analysis, like a triaxial fibre arrangement, will be considered to evaluate the deformation behaviour of a structure.

Figure 11: Thermal image of a specimen with integrated carbon-fibre sensor mesh

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